

Personality and Interpersonal Values as Predictors of Resilience among Young Adults

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A complex interaction of internal resources, social systems, and environmental factors influences resilience. The present study has attempted to investigate whether personality traits and interpersonal values are predictors of resilience in young adults. A convenient sample of 316 young adults between the age group of 18-25 years, who were pursuing undergraduate and postgraduate courses from two higher education institutions in the Coimbatore district, participated in the study. The sample was administered with Differential Personality Scale (DPS; Agrawal, 1996), the Circumplex Scale of Interpersonal Values (CSIV; Locke, 2000), and the Bharathiar University Resilience Scale (BURS; Annalakshmi, 2009). The results of multiple linear regression analyses indicated that conformity ($p < .001$) was a negative predictor of resilience, whereas interpersonal values such as dominance ($p < .001$) and extraversion ($p < .01$) were positive predictors of resilience, among young adults. Fostering positive personality traits and interpersonal values connected with resilience helps in improving the wellbeing of young adults.

Keywords: Resilience, interpersonal values, personality traits, young adults

Psychological resilience can be defined as a changing process where people keep up optimistic adjustment even under very difficult situations (Luthar & Cicchetti, 2000). Resilience is generally considered as a positive personality trait that helps a person to adapt more easily to life (Wagnild & Young, 1993). A variety of factors, such as personal attributes, as well as biological and environmental factors like social support, family ties, cultural practices, and societal norms play a part in determining resilience. The interplay of these factors is complex and determines the strength of a person when facing hardships (Curtis & Cicchetti, 2003). People who are less neurotic and more extraverted, open, agreeable, and conscientious are generally more resilient when facing adversity (Oshio et al., 2018; Womble et al., 2013). More resilient people are generally less impulsive, more cognitively organized, more enduring, more dominant, and more interpersonal with regards to affiliation, nurturance, and exhibition, emphasizing the important function of needs within the personality to be resilient (Annalakshmi, 2008). A strong family conformity was a significant factor in adolescents'

resilience, which pointed out the protective role of family values in resilience development (Ramadhana et al., 2023). Older people have more intense preferences for conformity, kindness, and self-reliance compared to younger people, while conformity is the one that grows the most with age (Afrose & Chowdhury, 1990). Individuals who feel tense and stressed seem to express lower levels of resilience, which suggests that a negative relation exists between them (Montero-Marin et al., 2014). Women who have balanced personality attributes have been shown to experience more happiness and resilience in life (Foumani et al., 2015). The development of healthy personality traits may result in enhancing adolescents' psychological resilience (Fayombo, 2010). While transitioning into adulthood, resilience is intimately connected with the attributes of conscientiousness, neuroticism, and extraversion; females outscore males in predicting resilience attributes of conscientiousness and neuroticism (Ercan, 2017). This illustrates the vital role that personality characteristics play in the process of people coping with and surviving hardships, thus stressing the intricate connection between individual traits and strength during challenging periods.

Interpersonal values are an important factor in determining the manner in which people interact socially among each other, and interfere positively with the aspect of resilience. Wiggins' (1995) circumplex model of interpersonal octants gives a clear and refined framework for not only understanding interpersonal dynamics but also evaluating to what extent interpersonal values influence social interactions. It has been found that the most important factor in interpersonal relationships is warmth, which in turn leads to higher resilience and better overall mental health (Theron et al., 2022). Also, extraversion is recognized as a positive trait associated with resilience, thus implying that people who are sociable and friendly might have a better ability to recover from adversity (Hähnchen, 2022; Khosbayan et al., 2022; Nieto et al., 2022; Singh & Singh, 2022; Soni, 2021; Singh, 2020). Those characterized by low psychoticism, high extraversion, and low neuroticism showed significantly more resilience, which highlights that emotional

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stability, sociability, and reduced hostility are three factors that independently and collectively build a strong resilient personality (Annalakshmi, 2007). Resilience is regarded as the mediator in the relationship between extraversion and happiness and positive and negative affect (Lü et al., 2014). Interpersonal value is generally experienced as promoting close relationships, although some means of pursuing it, such as perfectionism and dominance, may affect relationship quality (Lemay et al., 2021).

Several studies have underscored a strong relationship between personality traits and resilience. The present study aims to identify whether there is any relationship between personality traits and interpersonal values on one hand, and resilience on the other.

Method

Participants

A convenient sample of 316 young adults aged between 18-25 years (Males 54.1% & females 45.9%) studying in colleges located in Coimbatore were included in the study. One college and one university in Coimbatore were selected through convenient sampling. The inclusion criteria for the current study include undergraduate and postgraduate students currently enrolled in a recognized institution. The exclusion criteria include those who were unable to provide informed consent. Notably, most participants were 18 years old (30.4%). Academically, 63.5 % are UG students, while 36.5 % are PG students.

Measures

Differential Personality Scale (PD; Agrawal, 1996). The scale measures four factors along with 15 items that measure the individual's self-concept. The four factors are conformity vs. non conformity, tough-mindedness vs. tender-mindedness, normalcy, and tenseness. A higher score on each of the above subscales indicates a higher level of conformity, tough-mindedness, normalcy, and tenseness, respectively. Respondents are prompted to select a column from a scale of 1 (*negative pole*) to 7 (*positive pole*), representing two extremes, based on which trait they feel best describes them. Cronbach's alpha was .64, .59, .63 and .69 respectively for conformity, tough-mindedness, normalcy and tenseness in the present sample.

Circumplex Scale of Interpersonal Values (CSIV; Locke, 2000). It is a 64-item self-report tool created to complement interpersonal circumplex measures, efficiently gauging a broad range of agentic

and communal values related to interpersonal behaviour. It consists of eight 8-item scales with a circumplex structure. The items range from 0 (*not important to me*) to 4 (*extremely important to me*). The eight octants are assured-dominant, gregarious-extraverted, warm-agreeable, unassuming-ingenuous, unassured-submissive, aloof-introverted, cold-hearted, arrogant-calculating. These octants describe 4 dimensions, namely, assured-dominant, gregarious-extraverted, warm-agreeable, and unassuming-ingenuous. The scores on unassured-submissive, aloof-introverted, cold-hearted, arrogant-calculating were reverse-scored and added to the respective subscale indicative of that dimension. Thus, four scores were arrived at, namely, assured-dominant, gregarious-extraverted, warm-agreeable, and unassuming-ingenuous. Cronbach's alpha was .72, .73, .75 and .73 respectively for dominant, warmth, unassuming and extraversion in the present sample.

Bharathiar University Resilience Scale (BURS; Annalakshmi, 2009). It is a 30-item questionnaire that assesses an individual's duration of time it takes to return to normal after adverse events, responses to negativity and risk factors, perceptions of past negative events, and confidence in facing future challenges. The scale is a self-reporting tool, and each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (*not at all appropriate*) to 5 (*most appropriate*). A higher total score indicates greater resilience. Cronbach's alpha for the scale was found to be .79 in the present sample.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analysed using multiple linear regression analyses.

Procedure

Data collection began with obtaining formal permission from college authorities and was scheduled at the convenience of the students. A brief introduction about the study was given, and written informed consent was collected from those willing to participate. Selected survey measures were administered to groups of participants with appropriate instructions in their classroom setting during college working hours. The questionnaire completion took approximately 1 hour per participant.

Results

Multiple linear regression analyses were carried out to examine personality predictors of resilience among young adults. The results are presented below:

Table 1

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Gender, Conformity, Tough-Mindedness, Normalcy and Tenseness as Predictors of Resilience (N=316)

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t
	B	Std. Error	β	
Gender	-2.137	1.834	-.064	-1.165 ^{ns}
Conformity	-.730	.197	-.232	-3.703***
Tough-mindedness	-.259	.254	-.056	-1.021 ^{ns}
Normalcy	-.249	.235	-.071	-1.060 ^{ns}
Tenseness	-.141	.236	-.038	-.599 ^{ns}

Note. $R^2 = .105$, Adjusted $R^2 = .091$, $F(5, 310) = 7.308$, *** $p < .001$, ns = not significant.

The multiple regression analysis (see Table 1) for overall predictor variables produced $R^2 = .105$, $F(5, 310) = 7.308$, $p < .001$. Among the predictors, conformity significantly and negatively predicted resilience ($\beta = -.232$, $p < .001$), indicating that higher scores on this

dimension were associated with lower resilience. The other personality traits, tough-mindedness, normalcy, and tenseness, do not significantly affect resilience. Gender does not significantly predict resilience.

Table 2

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Gender, Dominance, Warmth, Unassuming, and Extraversion Predicting Resilience among Young Adults (N=316)

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t
	B	Std. Error	β	
Gender	.166	1.981	.005	.084 ^{ns}
Dominant	4.594	1.071	.240	4.291***
Warmth	.820	1.021	.057	0.804 ^{ns}
Unassuming	-1.337	1.023	-.083	-1.307 ^{ns}
Extraversion	3.579	1.118	.206	3.202**

Note. $R^2 = .125$, Adjusted $R^2 = .111$, $F(5, 310) = 8.863$, *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$. ns = not significant.

The multiple linear regression analysis (see Table 2) for the overall predictor variables produced $R^2 = .125$, $F(5, 310) = 8.863$, $p < .001$. Among the predictors, the dominant interpersonal value emerged as a significant positive predictor of resilience ($\beta = .240$, $p < .001$). Extraversion also significantly and positively predicted resilience ($\beta = .206$, $p < .01$). The interpersonal values of warmth and unassumingness, as well as gender, do not significantly predict resilience.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate whether personality traits and interpersonal values predict resilience among young adults.

The present study shows that the conformity personality trait negatively predicted resilience. This implies that individuals with conformist tendencies may be less resilient in facing challenges. Previous studies have mixed findings with regard to the relationship between conformity and resilience (Priya & Srivastava, 2019; Ramadhana et al., 2023) found a positive association between conformity and resilience. However, the finding of the present study is in line with a few previous studies that report a correlation between conformity and personality traits associated with resilience in the expected direction. Conformity is found to be negatively correlated with extraversion and openness (DeYoung et al., 2002), and both of these traits are positively correlated with resilience (Hähnchen, 2022; Baiju & James, 2024; Nieto et al., 2022; Khosbayan et al., 2022; Burtaverde et al., 2021). High conformity can lead to excessive reliance on external approval and reduced confidence in personal problem-solving abilities, which lowers self-efficacy and, in turn, weakens resilience by diminishing belief in one's ability to overcome adversity (Bandura, 1997). Individuals high on conformity are either motivated by their desire for social acceptance or by their belief that others have more accurate information than they and trust others' decisions, both indicating an external locus of control. Resilience is linked to an internal locus of control (Sharma, 2024; Hlondo & Zokaitluangi, 2024; Khalil & Esawi, 2024). Highly conforming individuals may also have less courage to question or challenge the social group of which they are a part. Authenticity was positively linked to resilience (Papasava et al., 2024). Authentic living endorses

living in alignment with one's core values and expressing them openly without camouflaging or attempting to align with others who have conflicting opinions. Thus, not fearing to express oneself instead of conforming to others may support resilience.

We also found that the interpersonal value of dominance emerged as a strong predictor of resilience. Individuals high on the dominance trait are confident, assertive, and have a tendency to take charge without aggression. All these characteristics are more likely to help them cope effectively with stress and adversity. The present finding that dominance positively predicted resilience among young adults aligns with prior evidence, as assertive and dominant ('forceful') traits significantly enhanced resilience in breast cancer patients (Annalakshmi et al., 2025). Internal protective factors like self-esteem (Pargas et al., 2010; Dumont & Provost, 1999; Karatas & Cakar, 2011; Barmola & Saini, 2024; Khosla & Mitra, 2025) and self-confidence (Çutuk et al., 2020) support resilience. Individuals with high self-esteem and self-confidence may be open to explore different coping strategies when facing a challenge without succumbing to feelings of helplessness. In contrast, those with low self-esteem may be more vulnerable to negative and challenging situations, resulting in negative attributions in the context of adversity (Nima et al., 2013; Orth et al., 2014).

The results of the present study show that extraversion had a positive impact on resilience. Extraversion related traits like being forceful and sociable were positively associated with resilience in a clinical sample (Annalakshmi et al., 2025). It was further supported by earlier studies which showed a strong relationship between extraversion and resilience (Singh & Singh, 2022; Soni, 2021; McDonnell & Semkovska, 2020) and at the same time, it is also in line with research which showed resilience is positively linked to personality traits, particularly in the areas where social support is the main source of coping (Campbell-Sills et al., 2005). Resilience is shaped by dominant interpersonal behaviors (Klainin-Yobas et al., 2021). Extraverts are more likely to seek social support (Kalra & Gautam, 2024; Kashif et al., 2023) a behaviour which can be helpful when facing obstacles. Extraversion includes psychological factors like optimism, enthusiasm, and self-esteem (Goldberg, 1990), and extraverts have flexible adaptation capabilities (Morales-Vives et

al., 2020), and view ambiguous life events as challenging and not threatening (Penley & Tomaka, 2002). The extravert personality includes psychological factors like positivity, enthusiasm, and self-esteem (Goldberg, 1990), and they have flexible adaptation competences (Morales-Vives et al., 2020), and view uncertain life events as a challenge and not as a threat (Penley & Tomaka, 2002). Moreover, extraversion strengthens social support, problem-solving, and cognitive restructuring (Connor-Smith & Flachsbar, 2007) all of which are likely to contribute to the emergence of resilience.

The present study showed that traits such as tough-mindedness, normalcy, and tenseness did not predict resilience. Previous studies, however, report that tenseness is negatively correlated with resilience (Montero-Marín et al., 2014). This finding is in contrast to earlier research, which suggested that tenseness tends to be negatively linked with resilience (Montero-Marín et al., 2014). Interpersonal values like warmth and unassuming did not predict resilience in the present study. However, earlier research has identified warmth in relationships as a key component in promoting resilience (Theron et al., 2022). The lack of significant results for interpersonal traits such as warmth and unassuming may be linked to the factors specific to the developmental stage of the sample. In the case of young adults in college environments, social behavior and interpersonal participation often show limited variance, which may reduce the effectiveness of interpersonal value measures in predicting outcomes (Arnett, 2000). Resilience is more closely linked to internal self-regulatory skills like believing in one's capabilities, thinking, and abilities in problem-solving rather than to outward social behaviors or interpersonal traits for individuals in this developmental stage (Masten, 2014; Connor & Davidson, 2003). Gender did not predict resilience in the present study. However, previous studies found adolescent girls to exhibit lower resilience than boys (Akilandeswari & Annalakshmi, 2023; Annalakshmi et al., 2024). These differences may be because of developmental changes: in adolescent boys, heritability influences externalizing coping, while emerging adults see narrowed gaps as females enhance emotion-focused coping and networks. By early adulthood, both genders have had chances to build a fuller range of adaptive capabilities, explaining the reduced gender gap in our sample. The present study highlights the complex connections among personality traits, interpersonal values, and resilience.

Conclusion

Personality and interpersonal values significantly influence resilience in young adults. Conformity negatively predicts resilience, while interpersonal values such as dominance and extraversion contribute positively to resilience. Future research could examine the dynamics involved in how personality trait influences like resilience, dominance and extraversion, influence resilience while controlling for social and environmental factors. Interventions tailored to individuals with dominant qualities could enhance resilience by leveraging strengths such as assertiveness and empathy. Leadership programs and personality development programs for school children to nurture resilience early can also lead to better outcomes in adulthood.

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